

Original article

Multifunctional Therapeutic Evaluation of Silver Nanoparticles Derived from Grape Cluster Stems

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Abstract

Background: Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have gained considerable importance as the subject of a therapeutic potential, in particular when produced by ecologically friendly methods using plant-derived compounds. **Objective:** Use *Vitis vinifera* grape cluster stems extract to biosynthesize silver nanoparticles (AgNPs), and evaluated their antibacterial, anticancer, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties. **Methodology:** Green synthesis was done to obtain silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using extracts of the stems of the vine, *vitis vinifera*. The resultant nanoparticles were characterized by UV-Visible spectroscopy, fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). The biological efficacy of the synthesized AgNPs was evaluated through antibacterial activity, anticancer activity, DPPH radical-scavenging tests, and anti-inflammatory. **Result:** the synthesized AgNPs were characterized by an SPR peak at ~440 nm. Also, have largely spherical morphology, with particle sizes ranging from (36.92-78.02 nm), and clustering primarily within 40-60 nm. The AgNPs showed antibacterial activity at a concentration of 1000 µg/mL. It had an inhibition zone of 30 mm against *Staphylococcus aureus*, 17 mm against *Enterococcus faecalis* and 16 mm against *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The anticancer ability was selective cytotoxicity with $IC_{50} = 336.9$ µg/mL of Hdfn and 212.5 µg/mL of MCF-7. The AgNPs reached ~60% DPPH radical scavenging at a concentration of 500 µg/mL. Also, at intermediate concentrations, a reduction ability of COX-2 expression. **Conclusion:** The grape cluster stems (*Vitis vinifera*) suitable source for the synthesis of AgNPs. The silver nanoparticles have a good ability as antibacterial, anticancer, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory with concentration-dependent effects.

Keywords: Antibacterial, Anticancer, Anti-inflammatory, Biomedical use, Grape cluster stems, Silver nanoparticles.

Received: 04.12.2025

Revised: 11.01.2026

Accepted: 13.01.2026

Published: 16.01.2025

Funding: This research did not receive any financial support.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

How to cite: Mshari A. Multifunctional Therapeutic Evaluation of Silver Nanoparticles Derived from Grape Cluster Stems. J Clin Pract Med Res, 2026;2(1):35-40. DOI: 10.59324/jcpmr.2026.2(1).06

Introduction

In last years, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have gained considerable importance as the subject of a therapeutic potential, in particular when produced by ecologically friendly (green) methods using plant-derived compounds [1]. The green synthesis approach uses phytochemicals present in plant extracts as reducing and stabilising agents to reduce the use of toxic reagents and high-energy systems. The reduction and capping agents in the biosynthesis process are phenolic compounds, flavonoids, vitamins, alkaloids, and terpenoids [2]. The production of AgNPs with plants is one of such promising avenues, as it can provide multifunctional bioactivities, including anti-bacterial [3], anticancer activity, anti-inflammation, and anti-oxidative [4].

Plant-mediated syntheses of AgNPs have high anti-bacterial effects against many Gram-positive and Gram-negative infections, including multidrug-resistant ones [5]. AgNPs interfere with bacterial survival in a variety of mechanisms; they include the induction of oxidative stress, destruction of proteins and cell membranes, and disturbance in DNA

replication. Moreover, they are able to lessen the attachment of bacteria and suppress the formation of biofilms, thereby resulting in their eventual death [6]. Moreover, AgNPs have been documented to have cytotoxic effects against cancer cells by mitochondrial dysfunction of cancer cells, activation of apoptosis pathways, generation of reactive oxygen species, and concentration-dependent selectivity in cancer cells [7].

AgNPs exhibit an excellent antioxidant activity that improves wound healing and underlines their prospects as natural treatment agents [8]. This has mostly been credited to phytochemicals that cover their surface which effectively neutralises reactive oxygen species and prevents oxidative tissue damage. The nanoparticles can alleviate oxidative stress, enhance the formation of collagen, and tissue remediation [9]. AgNPs have the ability to regulate the process of inflammation by reducing the emission of pro-inflammatory molecules and COX-2 gene expression and enhancing the anti-inflammatory molecules levels. These results indicate that AgNPs can exert a quantifiable anti-

inflammatory response since they can selectively suppress COX-2 signaling pathway and repress key inflammatory proteins [10]. *Vitis vinifera* (grape) is considered a resource rich in bioactive compounds. Using grape processing residue in nanoparticle synthesis provides economic value to agricultural waste streams and is consistent with circular bio-economy principles. *V. vinifera* extract-mediated AgNPs are a promising biological alternative for biomedical applications. To understand their mechanistic properties and therapeutic potential, they must be thoroughly characterized in terms of structural, morphological, and surface chemical aspects, as well as tested for antibacterial, antioxidant, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory effects.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of Plant Extracts

Vitis vinifera green grape cluster stems washed with distilled water. The samples were left to air-dry at room temperature for 5 to 7 days. They were dried after which they were grinded into a powder using an electric grinder. Then 35 g of the vegetal powder was mixed with 500 mL of deionized distilled water at 100 °C. The mixture was incubated, continuously stirred by 30 min at room temperature. The extract was then filtered under ambient conditions with the help of gauze pad and filter paper.

Preparation of Silver Nanoparticles

Preparation and synthesis of the AgNPs were based on Reddy *et al.* [11]. The silver nitrate solution was made by dissolving 0.08 g of silver nitrate in the required quantity of distilled water to produce a final volume of 500 mL. Then, the plant extract was dried at 40 °C and the solution was added. The incubation was done in the shaking incubator at 37°C in seven days. This was followed by harvesting the synthesized silver nanoparticles by transferring the solution to test tubes and centrifugation at a rate of 3000 rpm. The purification of the nanoparticles was followed by washing them with double-distilled water several times. The supernatant was disposed and the precipitate was harvested and washed again with deionized distilled water to achieve total purification. Lastly, the purified precipitate was dried and was ready to undergo the next experimental procedures.

Silver Nanoparticles Characterization

The characterization of the AgNPs was done by four methods, including ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) absorption spectroscopy, fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy analysis, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis, and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) analysis. The optical characteristics of synthesized silver nanoparticles were determined using UV-Vis spectrophotometry (Thermo, Biomate5). AgNPs were diluted using deionized water a number of times and the measurements were made in the wavelength range of (200-800 nm). The functional groups involved in the reduction of Ag⁺ were identified under FTIR Spectroscopy (IRAffinity-1, SHIMADZU), which was measured in the (400-4000 cm⁻¹) range. An XRD (Philips PW1730) has been used to analyse the crystallization characteristics of the AgNPs in the temperature range of 2 theta between 10 °C and 80 °C. FESEM was used in the analysis of the morphology and size of the synthesized AgNPs (TESCAN, MIRA3). The mean size of the particle was also calculated by obtaining the diameter of several nanoparticles with the Image J software. AgNPs had their type and proportion of elements identified using EDX. A zeta potential analyzer (HORIBA SZ-100) was used to test the stability of the NPs.

Antibacterial Activity of AgNPs

AgNPs were tested on the agar well diffusion technique Vijapur *et al.*, to assess the antibacterial efficacy against four pathogenic bacteria out of which three were multidrug-resistant (*Enterococcus faecalis*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) and the rest of the bacteria was resistant to methicillin (*Staphylococcus aureus*) [12]. A

bacterial suspension (equivalent to 0.5 McFarland standard) was evenly spread on the surface of Mueller-Hinton agar plates, using sterile cotton swabs. Subsequently, 100 µL of silver nanoparticle solutions (concentrations of 1000, 500, 250, 125, and 62.5 µg/mL) were carefully pipetted into wells (approximately 6 mm in diameter, which were made by a sterile cork borer). Additionally, 100 µL of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was added to a separate well to serve as a negative control. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h., after that, the diameters of the inhibition zones were measured in millimeters.

Anticancer Activity of AgNPs

The cytotoxic effects of AgNPs derived from *V. vinifera* stem were estimated according to Hussein *et al.* [13]. Used MTT assay (3-(4, 5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2, 5-diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide) on human breast cancer cell line (MCF-7) compared with human dermal fibroblasts, neonatal (HdFn) as a normal cell line. The concentrations 500, 250, 125, 62.5, and 31.25 µg/mL were applied for 48 hours to both MCF-7 and HdFn cell lines; after 4 hours of adding the MTT solution, the viability percentage and IC₅₀ were calculated.

Antioxidant Activity of AgNPs

The antioxidant activity of AgNPs was evaluated using the stable DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging assay, following the method described by Al-Saffar *et al.* [14]. 3 mL of methanol-DMSO (9:1v/v) and 0.3 mL of DPPH solution (0.1mg/mL) were added in separate reaction tubes with 0.5 mL of AgNPs (500, 250, 125, 62.5, and 31.25 µg/mL). The mixtures were shaken briefly and incubated in the dark at room temperature, for 1 hour. After that at 517 nm used to measured absorbance using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) reader. Methanol-DMSO mixture as negative control, and DPPH solution. Ascorbic acid considered as the reference standard.

Anti-inflammatory Effects of AgNPs on COX-2 Enzyme

According to the method of Ahn *et al.*, evaluated activity of AgNPs as anti-inflammatory [15]. The experiment depending on their effect on cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) enzyme expression. The concentrations 500, 250, 125, 62.5, and 31.25 µg/mL. were used in a cell culture assay. Cells were inoculated into microtiter plates (96-well) at 1×10⁵ cells/well and incubated at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere for overnight. After incubation, the medium was changed with fresh medium containing to specified concentrations of AgNPs. The cells were incubated for an additional 24 hours under identical conditions. Post-treatment, cells were harvested, and COX-2 enzyme expression levels were quantitatively analyzed using ELISA, following the protocol of the manufacturer. Control samples were treated with culture medium alone without nanoparticles.

Statistical Analysis

The antibacterial activity of data was analyzed used one-way analysis (SPSS version 23 software). Statistical significance was recognized if the p-value exceeded or equaled 0.05. Graph Pad Prism 10.4.0 was used to analyze the anticancer and antioxidant effects, and Origin Pro 10.15. for displaying the XRD findings and FTIR.

Results and Discussion

Biosynthesis of AgNPs

The result after seven days of incubation (Figure 1) showed, change in the reaction mixture color from yellowish-brown to deep-brown. The color change is considered the first sign of the formation of AgNPs. The color change could be due to components of the plant extract, have ability to reduce, capping, and stabilizing agents during the synthesis process [16]. Muhammad *et al.*, used grape juice and found the color change because of surface plasmon resonance, with plant-derived biomolecules which play an essential role in the reduction and stabilization of the nanoparticles [17].

Figure 1: The colour change and formation of AgNPs: 1. Aqueous extract of *Vitis vinifera* grape cluster stems 2. Immediately after adding AgNO_3 , 3. After incubation (7 days) with AgNO_3

Characterisation of the AgNPs

The UV-Vis result recorded a SPR peak at ~ 440 nm (Figure 2), this corresponding to the production of AgNPs. The location of the peak proves that the particles are mainly spherical and are located in the nanoscale since AgNPs tend to have the SPR bands at 400–460 nm depending on the size of the particle and the medium surrounding it [18]. The minor peak width suggests that the size distribution of the particles is uneven and this may be the normal default of chemical and biological syntheses [19].

Figure 2: The absorbance spectrum for the AgNPs (at 440nm)

The FTIR spectrum result for the aqueous extract (grape cluster stems) showed broad and strong absorption bands (Figure 3). In ~ 3433 cm^{-1} , agreement with stretching vibrations of hydroxyl (O-H) groups which present in alcohols and phenolic compounds. Additionally, significant bands appeared at ~ 2923 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching), ~ 1629 cm^{-1} (C=C aromatic stretching), ~ 1385 cm^{-1} (C-H bending), and ~ 1082 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching of phenolic and carbohydrate groups). While the synthesis AgNPs result (Figure 4) showed the same peaks of the functional group with slight peak shifts and reductions in band strength were observed. In particular, the changes in the O-H stretching band shifted from ~ 3433 to ~ 3439 cm^{-1} , also, the peaks at ~ 1629 and ~ 1082 cm^{-1} showed a little broadening. These little changes confirm the role of hydroxyl, carbonyl, and aromatic groups in the reduction of Ag^+ to Ag^0 and, the stabilizing of the nanoparticle surface. The decrease in peak intensities and shifts in functional group vibrations confirm that biomolecules in the plant extract acted as both reducing and capping agents [20]. These findings align with previously reported studies on the synthesis of silver nanoparticles using plant extracts as green synthesis [21,22].

Figure 3: FTIR spectrum analysis of the aqueous extract of *Vitis vinifera* grape cluster stems

Figure 4: FTIR spectrum analysis of AgNPs synthesized by the aqueous extract of grape cluster stems

The result of the SEM of the biosynthesized AgNPs using *Vitis vinifera* aqueous extract (Figure 5) showed predominantly spherical and quasi-spherical particles spread across the field. The particle diameters ranged approximately from 36.92 to 78.02 nm, with most particles clustered within the 40–60 nm range. Also, observed some particle aggregation, which is common in biomolecule-mediated synthesis. The morphology suggests successful nucleation and growth of AgNPs facilitated by phytochemicals in the plant extract. This result agrees with Michailidu *et al.*, who observed spherical and nanosized silver nanoparticles which synthesized by *Vitis vinifera* cane extract [23]. Also, Kara *et al.*, which used grape seeds [24].

Figure 5: The biosynthesized AgNPs under SEM

The EDX spectrum result (Figure 6) showed a declared and sharp signal at about 3 kiloelectron volt (keV). This is considered a feature of the SPR of metallic silver and confirmed the effective manufacturing of AgNPs. The other peaks detected belong to C, O, Si, Na, S, Cl, and P. These elements be associated with phytochemical residues and organic

stabilizing molecules originated from the extract. The result aligns with Hossain *et al.*, confirmed the reduction of Ag^+ to Ag^0 during recorded a strong Ag peak at ~3 keV [25]. The elements such as C and O considers natural reducing and capping agents [21]. The minor signals of Na, Si, P, S, and Cl indicate trace phytochemical and mineral residues from the extract, which are typical in green-synthesized AgNPs stabilized by natural bio-organic surface coatings [26].

Figure 6: The Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX) spectrum of silver nanoparticles from the aqueous extract of *Vitis vinifera* rachis

The Therapeutic Effect of AgNPs

Antibacterial activity of AgNPs

The antimicrobial assessment of the biosynthesized AgNPs (Figure 11 and Table 7) demonstrated a clear concentration-dependent inhibitory effect against all tested antibiotic-resistant bacteria (*S. aureus*, *E. faecalis*, *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa*). The highest inhibitory effect was observed at 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, with *S. aureus*, which showed the largest zone

of inhibition (30 mm), followed by *E. faecalis* (17 mm), *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa* (16 mm each). Significant reductions in activity were observed with decreased concentrations (500–62.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). While, no inhibition effect in the control group (DMSO) for any tested bacteria. These findings are in agreement with previous reports confirming that AgNPs demonstrated broad-spectrum antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria [27,28]. Besides of the AgNPs efficacy to their nanoscale size, also due to the large surface area to volume ratio. These can penetrate bacterial cell walls, causing cell structural changes and destroying the membrane, and even resulting in cell death. They can increase the permeability of the cell membranes, inhibit the replication of deoxyribonucleic acid by releasing silver ions, and create reactive oxygen species [29,30].

Figure 7: Antimicrobial activity test of AgNPs. A= *S. aureus*, B= *E. faecalis*, C= *E. coli*, D= *P. aeruginosa*, 1: 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. 2: 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. 3: 250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. 4: 125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. 5: 62.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. 6: DMSO

Table 1: The average of the growth inhibitory zone (mm) of AgNPs against antibiotic-resistant bacteria

No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Pathogen growth inhibitory zone (mm)			
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. faecalis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
1	1000	30	17	16	16
2	500	19	15	15	15
3	250	16	15	15	14
4	125	15	12	14	0
5	62.5	12	0	14	12
6	Control	0	0	0	0
P-value		0.001	0.001	0.001	0.01

Cytotoxicity Properties of AgNPs

The cytotoxicity evaluation of the biosynthesized AgNPs revealed a dose-dependent reduction in cell viability in both the cancerous MCF-7 and normal Hdfn cell lines (Figure 8). Cell viability decreased significantly with increasing AgNP concentration. In contrast, the Hdfn cells exhibited higher tolerance. MCF-7 cells showed a lower IC_{50} value (212.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) than Hdfn cells (336.9 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), indicating increased susceptibility of malignant cells to AgNP exposure. The result proved that AgNPs have a significantly selective cytotoxic effect against cancer cells than normal fibroblasts.

Figure 8: The cell percentage of the viability (MCF-7 and Hdfn cell line) after use of the AgNPs

Several previous studies documented the higher cytotoxicity of plant-mediated AgNPs against tumor cells, in contrast with the effect against the normal cells, which showed lower toxicity [31,32]. The cytotoxic reaction of MCF-7 is more than normal Hdfn cells, this is because of weak antioxidant defenses and an increase of the intrinsic oxidative stress in the cancer cells. The sensitivity of the cancer cells to the AgNP because it have high metabolic rates and ROS levels which led to oxidative damage and mitochondrial damage. While the normal cells more tolerance because they have effective antioxidant repairing systems [31,33]. This result improves the ability of the AgNPs as a promising potential therapeutic agent against cancer.

Effect of on COX-2 Expression and Inflammation

The result (Figure 9) recorded that the biosynthesized AgNPs in different concentrations (31.25–500 µg/ml) have an effect on the expression level of Cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2). The high concentration (500 µg/ml) showed a significant increase in COX-2 expression compared with the control (128.91 ng/mL). Although the other concentrations (250, 125, 62.5, and 31.25 µg/ml) showed no significant effect on the COX-2 levels, near or below the control, the highest reduction in COX-2 expression was particularly in 125 µg/mL. The COX-2 enzyme considered an essential for synthesis of pro-inflammatory prostaglandins, the lower expression level led to decrease in inflammatory reactions. The intermediate concentration of AgNPs blocks inflammatory signaling pathways which responsible to oxidative stress and cytokine activation [10]. A previous study showed, the high concentration of AgNPs induced an inflammatory stress reaction, while the moderate concentrations recorded therapeutic suppression of COX-2 [34]. Also, Other studies showed that the AgNPs able to regulate inflammatory pathways during the balance of the ROS-mediated signaling and cellular antioxidant ability [35,36].

Figure 9: The AgNPs activity as anti-inflammatory (* mean significant, ns mean no significant, $p < 0.05$)

AgNPs as an Antioxidant

The result (Figure 10) demonstrated that AgNPs have the ability to DPPH radical scavenging capacity. The result showed a concentration-dependent effect, with a high concentration the scavenging activity was about 60% and decreased at lower concentrations (250–31.1 µg/mL). The ascorbic acid showed good ability in scavenging activity in all tested concentrations. The AgNPs showed significant differences in antioxidant capability with slightly lower than ascorbic acid. The AgNPs have the ability of decreasing oxidative stress and stabilize free radicals through the transfer of hydrogen atoms or electrons. This ability come from the adsorbed phytochemical residues which formed during the green synthesis process [37]. The result agrees with a previous study that documented the synthesized AgNPs from grape pomace (*Vitis vinifera*) showed free radical scavenging activity (from 23% to 79%), also ascorbic acid (from 23% to 90%) in concentrations (from 20 to 100

µg/mL). Overall, AgNPs have antioxidant potential, driven by surface-bound bioactive compounds, which may be utilized in biomedical applications.

Figure 10: The AgNPs and ascorbic acid activity as antioxidant (DPPH mean 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl, NR mean AgNPs, ** mean $p < 0.01$ = significant)

Conclusion

This study confirms that grape cluster stems (*Vitis vinifera*) suitable source for the synthesis of AgNPs. The silver nanoparticles have a good ability as antibacterial, anticancer, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory with concentration-dependent effects. The current study needs more experiments in vivo and optimization of the concentration led to potential use in therapeutic application.

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